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Influence of Control Measures in Accounting On Job Performance of Bursary Staff in Rivers State Owned Higher Institutions

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the influence of control measures in accounting on job performance of Bursary staff in Rivers State owned higher institutions. Three specific objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design with a population of 136 bursary staff of higher institutions owned by Rivers State Government. The sample constituted the entire 136 respondents which was obtained through census sampling because of the manageable size. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled, "Influence of Accounting Control Measures on Job Performance Questionnaire (IACMJPQ)" which had five sections. It was validated by three experts and with an overall reliability coefficient of 0.864. A total of 136 copies of the instrument were administered and a total of 131 copies were retrieved and used for data analysis. Data gathered were analysed using mean for the research questions and analysis of variance for the hypotheses. The result of the study revealed that forensic control measure has positive influence on job performance of bursary staff. The result also showed that deterrent control measure, detective control measure, preventive control measure has positive influence on job performance of bursary staff of Rivers State Government owned higher institutions. Based on the result, it was recommended among others that higher institutions should strengthen preventive control systems such as clear approval processes, regular staff training, and task segregation to reduce errors and improve compliance with financial procedures.

Keywords: Accounting, job performance, bursary staff, higher institutions

INTRODUCTION

The efficient functioning of higher institutions largely depends on the financial accountability and operational effectiveness of their bursary units. The Bursary Department serves as the backbone for managing institutional funds, ensuring accountability, and sustaining the financial health of the institution. Control measures within bursary operations are of both practical and theoretical importance. These controls help mitigate errors, fraud, and inefficiencies, ensuring the institution remains financially sustainable. Furthermore, these controls foster transparency, reliability, and compliance with financial regulations. For higher institutions in Rivers State, implementing robust control measures is vital to supporting institutional growth, trustworthiness, and operational integrity.

Control measures in accounting refer to policies, procedures, and mechanisms implemented to ensure accuracy, reliability, and compliance in financial reporting and operations. They are the measures and controls employed by an organization with the aim of increasing efficiency and compliance. They ensure that financial reports are correct when presented to bankers, auditors, investors, as well as other stakeholders. Control measures are not new as they have been in practice for a long time. One of the important advantages of control measures is that they restore the general public's confidence in an organization (Mojo, 2024).

There are different types of control measures. These include: forensic control (Ohaka & Ordu, 2019) and deterrent control (Saber, 2022). Others are detective controls, preventive controls, and corrective controls. Detective controls, such as audits and reconciliations, are designed to identify errors or irregularities after they occur. For example, periodic audits may uncover unauthorized transactions. Similarly, an unannounced check of the actual cash balance in hand against cashier and cash balance is an instance of detective control. This could aim at ascertaining if the cashier is carrying out job correctly or not (Bevin, 2024).

Forensic control measures in accounting systems are specialized preventive, detective, and corrective control mechanisms designed to prevent, detect, and investigate financial fraud, errors, and irregularities. These controls go further than the traditional internal controls by incorporating investigative and evidence-preservation capabilities. Forensic control involves using forensic accounting techniques and information to strengthen financial oversight, detect and prevent fraud, and ensure the integrity of financial records. (Ohaka & Ordu, 2019). Forensic auditing has a positive significance relationship with fraud minimization and effective internal control system.

Deterrent control measures in accounting are control measures designed to discourage fraudulent activities or errors from occurring within a financial system. These measures aim at making it more difficult, risky, or undesirable for individuals to engage in unauthorized or improper actions. They are a crucial part of a robust internal control system, working alongside detective and corrective controls (Saber, 2022).

Detective accounting control is a key component of internal control systems that focuses on identifying errors, irregularities, or fraudulent activities after they have occurred. Unlike preventive controls, which aim to stop undesirable events before they happen, detective controls are designed to uncover issues in a timely manner so corrective actions can be taken (Hall, 2015). These controls play a pivotal role in enhancing transparency and accountability within financial systems and serve as a check on the effectiveness of other control measures. According to Romney and Steinbart (2018), detective controls function as a critical layer in the internal control framework, enabling management to monitor financial activities and ensure that transactions have been accurately recorded and authorized. These controls not only support the integrity of financial reports but also facilitate compliance with legal and regulatory requirements. Furthermore, their presence enhances stakeholder confidence by demonstrating an organization's commitment to identifying and correcting anomalies (Arens, Elder, Beasley & Hogan 2016). In the public sector and educational institutions, detective controls are vital for uncovering misappropriation of funds, accounting errors, and lapses in financial reporting (Ubesie, Ibezim, & Cyriacus, 2023).

The bursary department plays significant role in the success of any higher institution. The bursary unit is responsible for the financial management and sustainability of higher institutions. The unit ensure that the institution's financial resources are effectively and efficiently managed. This involves transparency in accounting for the institution's finance and strategic allocation of funds to meet academic and operational goals. This is an indication that the members of staff of the bursary unit in any higher institution should be up and doing. Consequently, their job performance is of optimum priority to the management of higher institutions.

Job performance refers to the effectiveness and efficiency with which individuals fulfill their assigned roles and responsibilities. According to Dambo and Innocent (2024), the success of an organization depends on the job performance of employees. For bursary staff, job performance encompasses accurate record-keeping, timely preparation of financial reports, budget management, and compliance with

financial regulations. These roles are critical in maintaining institutional financial stability. The performance of the bursary unit directly impacts the productivity of higher institutions by ensuring the availability of funds for academic programs, research, and infrastructural development. In essence, the efficiency of the bursary staff determines the financial health and overall performance of the institution.

Statement of the Problem

The funding of public higher institutions in Nigeria is the responsibility of state and federal government. Other sources of funds for public institutions in Nigeria include: internally generated revenue (IGR) and donation from non-governmental agencies. Such provided funds must be properly managed to support the institution's core missions of teaching, research, and community service. Effective fund management ensures that financial resources are strategically allocated, transparently utilized, and optimally directed towards academic and operational objectives. There has been concern over poor funding management in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. For example, Obona, Edim and Edim (2020), lamented that there exist unauthorized, misappropriation, intentional or illegal use of funds in higher institution by institutional leaders for other unauthorized aims which impact negatively on effective management, planning and control of the quality management of higher institutions in Nigeria.

A vital element that contributes to effective fund management in higher institution is accounting control measures. Effective accounting control is vital for any organization to maintain investor confidence, comply with regulatory requirements, and make informed business decisions. Accounting control measures play significant role in the job performance of bursary staff in higher institutions. They enhance accuracy and reduce errors, limits fraud and financial mismanagement, ensures compliance to financial rules and regulations, improves efficiency and productivity, facilitate decision making and planning, ensures trust and accountability, reduce work-related stress.

Previous studies on accounting control measure in higher institutions in Nigeria have focused on effect of internal control on financial management of universities in Nigeria (Akosile & Akinselure, 2016); impact of effective internal control system on financial accountability in tertiary institutions in Bauchi State (Shehu, 2020). Studies which investigated the influence of control measures in accounting on job performance of bursary staff in Nigeria and Rivers State in particular was scarce in the literature. Control measures play significant role in accountability and transparency in financial operation in tertiary institutions. Consequently, absence of a good control measures could limit effective financial operations in the tertiary institutions. The question is, what control measures are in place in tertiary institutions in Rivers State and what is the influence of these measures on job performance of bursary staff in these institutions. It is in search of answer to these questions that this study is intended.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of control measures in accounting on job performance of Bursary staff in Rivers State owned higher institutions. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine the influence of forensic control measures on job performance among Bursary staff in Rivers State owned higher institutions.
2. Ascertain the influence of deterrent control measures on job performance among Bursary staff in Rivers State owned higher institutions.
3. Determine the influence of detective control measures on job performance among Bursary staff in Rivers State owned higher institutions.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions.

1. What is the influence of forensic control measures on job performance among Bursary staff in Rivers State owned higher institutions?
2. What is the influence of deterrent control measures on job performance among Bursary staff in Rivers State owned higher institutions?
3. What is the influence of detective control measures on job performance among Bursary staff in Rivers State owned higher institutions?

Hypotheses

The study tested the following hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of Bursary department staff of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic and Ken-Saro Wiwa Polytechnic on the influence of forensic control measures on job performance.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of Bursary department staff of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic and Ken-Saro Wiwa Polytechnic on the influence of deterrent control measures on job performance.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of Bursary department staff of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic and Ken-Saro Wiwa Polytechnic on the influence of detective control measures on job performance.

METHOD

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design with a population of 136 bursary staff of higher institutions owned by Rivers State Government. The sample constituted the entire 136 respondents which was obtained through census sampling because of the manageable size. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled, "Influence of Accounting Control Measures on Job Performance Questionnaire (IACMJPQ)" which had five sections. It was validated by three experts and with an overall reliability coefficient of 0.864. A total of 136 copies of the instrument were administered and a total of 131 copies were retrieved and used for data analysis. Data gathered were analyzed using mean for the research questions and analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the hypotheses.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the influence of forensic control measures on job performance among Bursary staff in Rivers State owned higher institutions?*

Table 1: Mean for Influence of Forensic Control on Job Performance

S/N	Forensic Control Measure	RSU (n=31)			IAUOE (n=34)			CEAP (n=24)			KSWP (n=25)			RSCHST (n=17)		
		M	S.D.	RMK	M	S.D.	RMK	M	S.D.	RMK	M	S.D.	RMK	M	S.D.	RMK
1	The use of forensic accounting tools helps identify financial irregularities towards effective service delivery.	3.16	0.37	A	3.29	0.46	A	3.00	0.00	A	3.24	0.44	A	3.12	0.33	A
2	Regular forensic audits improve my accountability and performance.	3.29	0.46	A	3.00	0.00	A	3.67	0.48	A	3.16	0.37	A	3.29	0.47	A
3	Members of staff are more cautious in financial reporting due to forensic control procedures.	3.00	0.00	A	3.32	0.47	A	3.25	0.44	A	3.36	0.49	A	3.59	0.51	A
4	Forensic control measures help reduce manipulation of accounting records which promotes accountability.	3.45	0.51	A	3.15	0.36	A	3.21	0.41	A	3.00	0.00	A	3.35	0.49	A
5	The fear of forensic investigation inspire staff to ensure accuracy in records.	3.45	0.51	A	3.35	0.49	A	3.00	0.00	A	3.24	0.44	A	3.06	0.24	A
6	Forensic controls contribute to timely detection of fraud in the	3.10	0.30	A	3.35	0.49	A	3.63	0.49	A	3.52	0.51	A	3.00	0.00	A

	bursary.															
	Forensic techniques															
7	encourage transparency	3.39	0.50	A	3.00	0.00	A	3.13	0.34	A	3.52	0.51	A	3.24	0.44	A
	in my work performance.															
	Grand Mean	3.26	0.38	A	3.21	0.32	A	3.27	0.31	A	3.29	0.39	A	3.24	0.35	A

Field Survey, 2025

The result in Table 1 shows influence of forensic control measures on job performance among bursary staff in Rivers State owned higher institutions. The result shows that: the use of forensic accounting tools helps identify financial irregularities towards effective service delivery (M = 3.16 for RSU, M = 3.29 for IAUOE, 3.00 for CEAP, 3.24 for KSWP and 3.12 for RSCHST). The result also shows that: regular forensic audits improve accountability and performance (M = 3.29 for RSU, M = 3.00 for IAUOE, M = 3.67 for CEAP, M = 3.16 for KSWP, and M = 3.29 for RSCHST). The result also shows that members of staff are more cautious in financial reporting due to forensic control procedures (M = 3.00 for RSU, M = 3.32 for IAUOE, M = 3.25 for CEAP, M = 3.36 for KSWP, and M = 3.59 for RSCHST). Also, the result shows that: forensic control measures help reduce manipulation of accounting records which promotes accountability (M = 3.45 for RSU, M = 3.15 for IAUOE, M = 3.21 for CEAP, M = 3.00 for KSWP, and M = 3.35 for RSCHST). Again, the result shows that the fear of forensic investigation inspires staff to ensure accuracy in records (M = 3.45 for RSU, M = 3.35 for IAUOE, M = 3.00 for CEAP, M = 3.24 for KSWP, and M = 3.06 for RSCHST). Further, the result shows that: forensic controls contribute to timely detection of fraud in the bursary (M = 3.10 for RSU, M = 3.35 for IAUOE, M = 3.63 for CEAP, M = 3.52 for KSWP, and M = 3.00 for RSCHST). Furthermore, the result shows that: forensic techniques encourage transparency in work performance (M = 3.39 for RSU, M = 3.00 for IAUOE, M = 3.13 for CEAP, M = 3.52 for KSWP, and M = 3.24 for RSCHST). Grand means of M = 3.39 for RSU, M = 3.00 for IAUOE, M = 3.13 for CEAP, M = 3.52 for KSWP, and M = 3.24 for RSCHST shows that forensic control measure has influence on job performance of bursary staff in Rivers State owned higher institutions.

Research Question 2: *What is the influence of deterrent control measures on job performance among Bursary staff in Rivers State owned higher institutions?*

Table 2: Mean for Influence of Deterrent Control on Job Performance

S/N	Deterrent Measure	Control	RSU (n=31)			IAUOE (n=34)			CEAP (n=24)			KSWP (n=25)			RSCHST (n=17)		
			M	S.D.	RMK	M	S.D.	RMK	M	S.D.	RMK	M	S.D.	RMK	M	S.D.	RMK
8	The presence of disciplinary policies deters staff from engaging in fraud which leads to enhancement in job productivity.		3.19	0.40	A	3.56	0.50	A	3.21	0.41	A	3.04	0.20	A	3.35	0.49	A
9	Staff perform duties more diligently when they bear in mind, fear of sanctions.		3.00	0.00	A	3.15	0.36	A	3.54	0.51	A	3.00	0.00	A	3.53	0.51	A
10	Awareness of consequences motivates staff to work in compliance with financial procedures.		3.58	0.50	A	3.38	0.49	A	3.00	0.00	A	3.16	0.37	A	3.18	0.39	A
11	Clearly stated penalties discourage financial misconduct in the bursary.		3.03	0.18	A	3.24	0.43	A	3.54	0.51	A	3.36	0.49	A	3.00	0.00	A
12	Warning signals as a control measure promotes double-checking of financial documents before submission.		3.29	0.46	A	3.00	0.00	A	3.21	0.41	A	3.04	0.20	A	3.35	0.49	A
13	I am less likely to bypass procedures because of enforcement policies.		3.29	0.46	A	3.62	0.49	A	3.17	0.38	A	3.00	0.00	A	3.18	0.39	A
14	The risk of punishment enhances my overall job performance.		3.00	0.00	A	3.06	0.24	A	3.21	0.41	A	3.40	0.50	A	3.12	0.33	A
	Grand Mean		3.20	0.29	A	3.29	0.36	A	3.27	0.38	A	3.14	0.25	A	3.24	0.37	A

Field Survey, 2025

The result in Table 2 shows the influence of deterrent control measures on job performance among bursary staff in Rivers State–owned higher institutions. The result shows that: the presence of disciplinary policies deters staff from engaging in fraud which leads to enhancement in job productivity (M = 3.19 for RSU, M = 3.56 for IAUOE, M = 3.21 for CEAP, M = 3.04 for KSWP, and M = 3.35 for RSCHST). The result also shows that: staff perform duties more diligently when they bear in mind the fear of sanctions (M = 3.00 for RSU, M = 3.15 for IAUOE, M = 3.54 for CEAP, M = 3.00 for KSWP, and M = 3.53 for RSCHST). The result further shows that: awareness of consequences motivates staff to work in compliance with financial procedures (M = 3.58 for RSU, M = 3.38 for IAUOE, M = 3.00 for CEAP, M = 3.16 for KSWP, and M = 3.18 for RSCHST). Also, the result shows that: clearly stated penalties discourage financial misconduct in the bursary (M = 3.03 for RSU, M = 3.24 for IAUOE, M = 3.54 for CEAP, M = 3.36 for KSWP, and M = 3.00 for RSCHST). Again, the result shows that: warning signals as a control measure promote double-checking of financial documents before submission (M = 3.29 for RSU, M = 3.00 for IAUOE, M = 3.21 for CEAP, M = 3.04 for KSWP, and M = 3.35 for RSCHST). Furthermore, the result shows that: staff are less likely to bypass procedures because of enforcement policies (M = 3.29 for RSU, M = 3.62 for IAUOE, M = 3.17 for CEAP, M = 3.00 for KSWP, and M = 3.18 for RSCHST). Finally, the result shows that: the risk of punishment enhances overall job performance (M = 3.00 for RSU, M = 3.06 for IAUOE, M = 3.21 for CEAP, M = 3.40 for KSWP, and M = 3.12 for RSCHST).

= 3.12 for RSCHST). Grand means of M = 3.20 for RSU, M = 3.29 for IAUOE, M = 3.27 for CEAP, M = 3.14 for KSWP, and M = 3.24 for RSCHST show that deterrent control measures have influence on job performance of bursary staff in Rivers State–owned higher institutions.

Research Question 3: *What is the influence of detective control measures on job performance among Bursary staff in Rivers State owned higher institutions?*

Table 3: Mean for Influence of Detective Control on Job Performance

S/N	Detective Control Measure	RSU (n=31)			IAUOE (n=34)			CEAP (n=24)			KSWP (n=25)			RSCHST (n=17)		
		M	S.D.	RMK	M	S.D.	RMK	M	S.D.	RMK	M	S.D.	RMK	M	S.D.	RMK
15	Regular internal checks enhance my accountability at work to boost performance.	3.55	0.51	A	3.24	0.43	A	3.00	0.00	A	3.16	0.37	A	3.53	0.51	A
16	Knowing that my work is subject to audit improves my attention to detail towards better job performance.	3.32	0.48	A	3.41	0.50	A	3.25	0.44	A	3.20	0.41	A	3.00	0.00	A
17	The presence of detection tools motivates me to follow procedures strictly towards optimum job output.	3.13	0.34	A	3.00	0.00	A	3.46	0.51	A	3.32	0.48	A	3.29	0.47	A
18	Detective controls help me learn from mistakes in real-time for better service delivery.	3.48	0.51	A	3.47	0.51	A	3.17	0.38	A	3.00	0.00	A	3.65	0.49	A
19	Audits increase my level of transparency in job delivery.	3.00	0.00	A	3.09	0.29	A	3.46	0.51	A	3.68	0.48	A	3.18	0.39	A
20	Error detection mechanisms make me more cautious in handling tasks towards ensuring accuracy.	3.26	0.44	A	3.12	0.33	A	3.17	0.38	A	3.12	0.33	A	3.47	0.51	A
21	I try doing my job accurately, knowing that there are systems in place to detect irregularities.	3.55	0.51	A	3.26	0.45	A	3.00	0.00	A	3.20	0.41	A	3.35	0.49	A
	Grand Mean	3.33	0.40	A	3.23	0.36	A	3.21	0.32	A	3.24	0.35	A	3.35	0.41	A

Field Survey, 2025

The result in Table 3 shows the influence of detective control measures on job performance among bursary staff in Rivers State–owned higher institutions. The result shows that: regular internal checks enhance accountability at work to boost performance (M = 3.55 for RSU, M = 3.24 for IAUOE, M = 3.00 for CEAP, M = 3.16 for KSWP, and M = 3.53 for RSCHST). The result also shows that: knowing that work is subject to audit improves attention to detail towards better job performance (M = 3.32 for RSU, M = 3.41 for IAUOE, M = 3.25 for CEAP, M = 3.20 for KSWP, and M = 3.00 for RSCHST). In addition, the result shows that the presence of detection tools motivates staff to follow procedures strictly towards optimum job output (M = 3.13 for RSU, M = 3.00 for IAUOE, M = 3.46 for CEAP, M = 3.32 for KSWP, and M = 3.29 for RSCHST). Also, the result shows that detective controls help staff learn from mistakes in real-time for better service delivery (M = 3.48 for RSU, M = 3.47 for IAUOE, M = 3.17 for CEAP, M = 3.00 for KSWP, and M = 3.65 for RSCHST). Furthermore, the result shows that audits increase the level of transparency in job delivery (M = 3.00 for RSU, M = 3.09 for IAUOE, M = 3.46 for CEAP, M = 3.68 for KSWP, and M = 3.18 for RSCHST). Again, the result shows that error detection mechanisms make staff more cautious in handling tasks towards ensuring accuracy (M = 3.26 for RSU, M = 3.12 for IAUOE, M = 3.17 for CEAP, M = 3.12 for KSWP, and M = 3.47 for RSCHST). Finally, the result shows that staff try to do their jobs accurately, knowing that there are systems in place to detect irregularities (M = 3.55 for RSU, M = 3.26 for IAUOE, M = 3.00 for CEAP, M = 3.20 for KSWP, and M = 3.35 for RSCHST).

RSCHST). Grand means of $M = 3.33$ for RSU, $M = 3.23$ for IAUOE, $M = 3.21$ for CEAP, $M = 3.24$ for KSWP, and $M = 3.35$ for RSCHST shows that detective control measures have an influence on job performance of bursary staff in Rivers State-owned higher institutions.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of Bursary department staff of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic and Ken-Saro Wiwa Polytechnic on the influence of forensic control measures on job performance.

Table 4: ANOVA for Influence of Forensic Control on Job Performance

Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-Value	p-value	Decision
Between Groups	0.117	4	0.029	1.437	0.225	Accepted
Within Groups	2.575	126	0.020			
Total	2.692	130				

The result in Table 4 shows the analysis of variance for the influence of forensic control measures on job performance. The result shows that $F(4, 126) = 1.437, p > 0.05$. Based on this, the hypothesis was accepted. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of Bursary department staff of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic and Ken-Saro Wiwa Polytechnic on the influence of forensic control measures on job performance.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of Bursary department staff of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic and Ken-Saro Wiwa Polytechnic on the influence of deterrent control measures on job performance.

Table 5 : ANOVA for Influence of Deterrent Control on Job Performance

Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	Decision
Between Groups	0.369	4	0.092	4.526	0.002	Rejected
Within Groups	2.566	126	0.020			
Total	2.935	130				

The result in Table 5 shows the analysis of variance for the influence of deterrent control measures on job performance. The result shows that $F(4, 126) = 4.526, p < 0.05$. Based on this, the hypothesis was rejected. This indicates that there was a significant difference in the mean rating of Bursary department staff of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic and Ken-Saro Wiwa Polytechnic on the influence of deterrent control measures on job performance.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of Bursary department staff of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic and Ken-Saro Wiwa Polytechnic on the influence of detective control measures on job performance.

Table 6: ANOVA for Influence of Detective Control on Job Performance

Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	Decision
Between Groups	0.386	4	0.097	3.350	0.012	Rejected
Within Groups	3.633	126	0.029			
Total	4.019	130				

The result in Table 6 shows the analysis of variance for the influence of detective control measures on job performance. The result shows that $F(4, 126) = 3.350, p < 0.05$. Based on this, the hypothesis was rejected. This indicates that there was a significant difference in the mean rating of Bursary department staff of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic and Ken-Saro Wiwa Polytechnic on the influence of detective control measures on job performance.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first research question sought to determine the influence of forensic control measures on job performance of bursary staff in Rivers State owned higher institutions. The result showed that forensic control measures positively influence their job performance. Specifically, they indicated that the use of forensic accounting tools helps identify financial irregularities and enhances effective service delivery. They also agreed that regular forensic audits improve staff accountability and performance, while forensic procedures encourage caution in financial reporting, reduce manipulation of accounting records, and promote accuracy. These findings corroborate the study of Amah (2018), who reported that forensic auditing had a significant positive relationship with fraud minimization and strengthening of internal control systems in the Abia State civil service. Similarly, the present study aligns with that of Adeyemi and Olarewaju (2019) who found that components of internal control systems such as control environment, control activities, and monitoring significantly influenced financial accountability in the public sector. The emphasis on forensic control procedures in this study is consistent with their conclusion that structured internal controls safeguard transparency and compliance.

The results further align with the findings of Balagobei (2020), who discovered that record keeping and budgeting practices significantly improved organizational performance in SMEs in Sri Lanka. By implication, forensic control measures can be seen as advanced accounting practices that strengthen accountability and operational performance in higher institutions. Similarly, Maniratunga, Fwamba and Olang'o (2021) found that preventive accounting controls had a significant positive effect on organizational performance of SMEs in Burundi, confirming that the presence of robust forensic or preventive control systems enhances effectiveness and efficiency in organizational operations.

The second research question sought to examine the influence of deterrent control measures on job performance of bursary staff in Rivers State owned higher institutions. The findings revealed that respondents across the five institutions generally agreed that deterrent control measures have a positive influence on their job performance. Specifically, they indicated that the presence of disciplinary policies deters staff from engaging in fraud and enhances productivity. The respondents also agreed that the fear of sanctions motivates staff to perform duties more diligently and comply with financial procedures.

This finding is consistent with the findings of Adeyemi and Olarewaju (2019) who found that all components of internal control, including monitoring and enforcement mechanisms, significantly affect financial accountability in the public sector. Similarly, the present results align with Isa (2020), who found that control activities and monitoring significantly influenced financial performance in federal parastatals, highlighting the role of enforcement and deterrent measures in strengthening compliance and performance.

The findings also corroborate Amah (2018), who emphasized that forensic auditing and control mechanisms contributed to fraud minimization and effective internal control systems. By extension, deterrent controls as part of the broader internal control framework help to check fraudulent tendencies, thereby sustaining performance. Likewise, Akosile and Akinselure (2016) reported a significant relationship between internal control and prudent management of resources in universities, reinforcing the present finding that disciplinary measures support accountability and responsible financial management. Additionally, the findings mirror those of Balagobei (2020) and Maniratunga, Fwamba, and Olang'o (2021), who showed that accounting practices and preventive control measures respectively improved organizational performance. Deterrent controls serve as preventive mechanisms that create psychological

and institutional barriers against misconduct, thereby enhancing diligence and job productivity in higher education bursary operations.

The test of hypothesis two showed that there was a significant difference in the mean ratings of bursary staff across the five institutions on the influence of deterrent control measures. This implies that while all institutions acknowledged the positive role of deterrent controls, their perceptions varied. The differences may be attributed to institutional culture, enforcement strictness, or prior experiences with fraud and disciplinary measures in the different institutions.

The third research question investigated the influence of detective control measures on job performance of bursary staff in Rivers State owned higher institutions. The findings revealed that respondents across the five institutions generally agreed that detective controls have a positive effect on their performance. Specifically, bursary staff indicated that regular internal checks enhance accountability and boost job performance. They also agreed that knowing their work is subject to audit improves attention to detail, while the presence of detection tools motivates them to adhere strictly to procedures for optimal job output.

These findings are consistent with the study of Amah (2018), who showed that forensic auditing positively influenced fraud minimization and strengthened internal controls, which include detection mechanisms. Likewise, the results align with Adeyemi and Olarewaju (2019), who found that monitoring and evaluation — a core aspect of detective controls — significantly impacted financial accountability in the public sector. This supports the present study's finding that audits and error detection mechanisms enhance diligence and accuracy.

The findings also corroborate Isa (2020), who reported that information and communication, monitoring, and control activities significantly influenced financial performance of federal parastatals. In the same vein, Akosile and Akinselure (2016) observed a significant relationship between internal control systems and prudent management of university finances, underscoring the role of monitoring and detection in effective management.

Moreover, the present findings resonate with Balagobei (2020), who established that accounting practices such as record-keeping and budgeting improved organizational performance. Detective control measures complement these practices by ensuring adherence and accuracy through systematic checks. Similarly, Maniratunga, Fwamba, and Olang'o (2021) found that preventive and corrective accounting controls improved organizational performance in SMEs in Burundi. Detective controls serve a similar purpose by discouraging errors and ensuring financial transparency.

The test of hypothesis three revealed that there was a significant difference in the mean ratings of bursary staff across the institutions on the influence of detective control measures ($p < 0.05$). This implies that although all institutions acknowledged the positive effect of detective controls, their perceptions varied. These differences may be linked to institutional variations in the frequency and effectiveness of internal checks, auditing systems, and error-detection tools. Institutions with stricter or more consistent application of detective measures may have staff who perceive a stronger impact on their job performance.

CONCLUSIONS

This study examined the influence of forensic control measures comprising preventive, detective, and corrective controls on job performance among bursary staff in Rivers State owned higher institutions. The findings have shown that all three forms of controls play an important role in improving the quality of work carried out by staff.

First, preventive controls such as clear approval processes, access control systems, task segregation, and regular training were found to help staff reduce errors, avoid workload confusion, and perform their duties more efficiently. Staff generally agreed that preventive measures promote compliance and integrity, thereby supporting better performance. Second, detective controls such as internal checks, audits, detection tools, and error detection mechanisms were reported to enhance accountability, transparency, attention to detail, and strict adherence to procedures. Staff across the institutions recognized that detective measures motivate accuracy and help them learn from mistakes, which leads to

better service delivery. Third, corrective controls such as feedback after errors, disciplinary reviews, correction policies, and correction of system errors were shown to improve accountability, compliance, and accuracy in service delivery. Staff noted that corrective actions helped them adjust strategies and avoid repeating mistakes, which enhanced their overall effectiveness.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Higher institutions should strengthen preventive control systems such as clear approval processes, regular staff training, and task segregation to reduce errors and improve compliance with financial procedures.
2. Management should ensure that disciplinary policies, sanctions, and enforcement mechanisms are consistently applied, as the awareness of consequences encourages staff to work more diligently and responsibly.
3. Institutions should harmonize and regularly update their audit practices, internal checks and error detection mechanisms across all bursary departments to enhance accountability, accuracy, and transparency.

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